

How Do Digital Technologies Drive the Transformation of Secondary Vocational English Teaching? — Based on 36 Practical Cases in China (2025)

Yanjun Liu

Dongguan Light Industry School
Email: 574936721@qq.com

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Abstract

Based on 36 practical cases of secondary vocational English teaching, this paper systematically sorts out the paths of teaching reform empowered by digital technologies. The study finds that technologies such as artificial intelligence, blended teaching, and virtual simulation have promoted the transformation of teaching models towards personalization and contextualization by building a "diagnosis-connection-integration" precision teaching system, an "online + offline" blended closed loop, and immersive vocational scenarios. At the level of core literacy cultivation, a digital training path of "language ability + vocational skills + cultural awareness" has been formed, which effectively improves students' adaptability to jobs and cross-cultural communication skills. Rural secondary vocational schools have broken through development bottlenecks through resource sharing and teacher training, and special majors (such as computer science, electronic technology, and tea industry) have realized the integration and innovation of "English + major". Meanwhile, teachers' digital literacy has been significantly improved through the "training-teaching research-incentive" system, but there are still challenges in practice such as superficial application of technology and insufficient resource adaptability. The research provides a replicable paradigm for digital teaching of secondary vocational English, helping the integration of "post-course-competition-certificate" and the cultivation of high-quality technical and skilled talents.

Keywords: Secondary vocational English; Digital technologies; Teaching model innovation; Core literacy

1. Introduction

Under the strategic background of the digital transformation of vocational education, secondary vocational English teaching is undergoing a profound reform from traditional "knowledge imparting" to the integration of "post-course-competition-certificate". The Vocational Education Law (revised in 2022) clearly puts forward the requirements of "integration of production and education, school-enterprise cooperation", emphasizing the accurate connection between teaching content and job needs. However, the current secondary vocational English teaching still faces practical difficulties such as the disconnection between curriculum content and industry needs, insufficient practical ability of students, and a single evaluation method. Through the keyword frequency analysis of 165 national educational technology papers related to "secondary vocational English" in 2025, the rapid development of digital technologies provides a new path to solve the above problems. Technologies such as artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and big data are promoting the transformation of secondary vocational English teaching towards personalization, contextualization, and professionalism by reconstructing teaching processes, creating vocational scenarios, and optimizing evaluation systems(Wang, X. G, 2025).

Based on 36 practical cases of secondary vocational English teaching (Table 1), this paper systematically sorts out the innovation of teaching models, the cultivation paths of core literacy, and the practical effects empowered by digital technologies. These cases cover multiple themes such as AI learning situation diagnosis, blended teaching, virtual simulation training, and cross-cultural communication cultivation, involving multiple majors such as computer science, tourism, e-commerce, and electronic technology, presenting the exploration experiences of different regions (including rural secondary vocational schools) in digital reform.

Through the integrated analysis of the above cases, this paper aims to extract the core characteristics and practical paradigms of digital teaching of secondary vocational English, provide theoretical references for deepening the "three teachings" reform in vocational education, and provide replicable and promotable operation paths for front-line teachers, ultimately promoting the qualitative leap of secondary vocational English teaching from "disconnection between learning and application" to "integration of post and course".

Table 1. 36 practical cases of secondary-vocational(SV) English

No.	Regional Location	Application Scenario	Main Content	Effectiveness
1	/	SV English	Build "Diagnosis-Connection-Linkage" 3D teaching system, integrating intelligent gap diagnosis, virtual training, and blockchain-based 1+X certification.	Improved vocational English ability; 82% VETS pass rate (41% higher than control group).
2	/	SV English	Optimize teaching via AI tools (intelligent platform, speech recognition) to shift learning from passive to autonomous.	Experimental group: avg. score 85.4 (control 77.9), task completion 92.6% (78.2%), speech score 87.3 (72.5%), writing error rate 8.1% (14.6%).
3	/	SV English	Develop "pre-class preview-assessment + in-class intelligent interaction + after-class consolidation" smart classroom mode (applied in English 2 Unit 5).	Enhanced interactivity/participation; improved English pragmatics via AI-generated scenarios; higher teaching efficiency.
4	/	SV English Writing	Integrate Doubao AI for peer review (AI-assisted framework, process innovation, teacher role positioning).	Grammar errors reduced from 11.3 to 3.8 per article (66.4% drop); cohesive words increased from 2.8 to 6.5 types; 87% students liked it.
5	Hainan	Secondary Vocational Tourism English ("Food" unit)	Build "Culture-Language-Practice" 3-in-1 mode via PBL, integrating Deepseek, Doubao, etc., around "Hainan healthy diet pyramid".	Vocabulary +200; 95% diet vocabulary mastery; grammar errors -30%; oral fluency +40%; related videos >100k views.
6	Dongyang	SV English Writing	Develop automatic correction/feedback via AIGC	Higher correction efficiency/accuracy; improved

			(DeepSeek) for dynamic resources and personalized support.	writing accuracy/logic; eased "large-scale teaching vs. personal needs" conflict.
7	/	SV English	Adopt AI + portraits for precise lesson preparation, in-depth learning ecology, and real-time feedback evaluation.	More accurate lesson prep; reduced teacher burden; formed "evaluation-prep-teaching-learning-evaluation" loop.
8	A county	Secondary Vocational Automobile Repair English	Build "ideological-political + professional + language" 3D model via national smart platform, using "6-step digital teaching".	Pass rate +28% (p<0.001); underachievers' professional English +47.3% (d=0.87); graduate adaptation period -62.5%.
9	/	SV English Writing	Apply POA ("driving-facilitating-evaluating") with network/big data, linking reading and writing (plus micro-writing).	Boosted writing interest/participation; promoted teaching reform; improved comprehensive language ability.
10	/	SV English ("Marco Polo..." in Basic Module 2)	Use digital mode (animation, virtual connection) with task-driven/situational methods to address difficulties.	Stimulated interest; met personal needs; improved efficiency; cultivated comprehensive ability.
11	/	Secondary Vocational Tourism English (Listening & Speaking, "Enjoy the Festival")	Teach via Seewo Whiteboard with "preview-guide-determine-explore-practice-display-evaluate-expand" process, integrating tour guide scenarios.	Enhanced interest; integrated language/professional skills; cultivated core/occupational literacy.
12	Mountainous areas	SV English	Build "resource integration-situation creation-interaction-feedback-extension" mode via "He Education" platform.	Experimental group: post-test avg. 78.5 (control 63.2); situational questions 72% (45%); 85% liked digital tools.
13	/	SV English + ICH + skills (Unit 6, English 2)	Integrate ICH terms (DeepSeek), interaction (Seewo), and SPSS analysis for interdisciplinary mode.	Improved language application; higher Unit 6 vocabulary usage/passive voice accuracy; deeper craftsman spirit understanding.
14	/	SV English (interdisciplinary)	Use immersive tech, AI personalized training, and big data	Broke disciplinary barriers; improved interdisciplinary thinking/language ability; improved

		ry)	for precise diagnosis.	evaluation system.
15	/	SV English	Build "online + offline teacher" dual-teacher class via national smart platform's "scenario collaboration".	Resource sharing; higher participation; better personalized learning; more efficient teacher collaboration.
16	/	Secondary Vocational Live E-Commerce English	Develop "goal-content-mode-evaluation" 4D strategy with VR/AI, integrating English and live operation skills.	Experimental group: oral avg. 85 (control 68); industry terms 90% correct (56%); 80% competent in basic cross-border live broadcast.
17	Wenzhou	Secondary Vocational Aviation English + local ICH	Apply "AI-CULTURE" mode with generative AI, multimodal resources, VR via 9-stage process.	ICH English expression: 62.3→76.8; cross-cultural communication: 58.7→72.8; improved digital skills/cultural sensitivity (p<0.001).
18	Dongguan	SV English	Adopt "zero-cost digital + localized textbooks" model via "tool-resource-teaching-evaluation-ecology" matrix.	More interactions; 3-hour less lesson prep time; "dual database + 1 mode" system radiated to Shantou, Jieyang.
19	/	SV English	Use multi-dimensional data pool (static/dynamic/behavioral/emotional) for personalized teaching.	Higher participation/grades (esp. oral/listening); homework completion 75%→91%; overdue rate halved; listening/speaking +11 points.
20	/	Computer Application Professional English	Integrate flowchart-based exclamation sentence teaching via observation/practice.	Deeper grammar understanding; higher participation; better autonomous learning ability/interest.
21	/	SV English (mechanical & electrical)	Blended teaching (pre-class online preview + in-class offline interaction + after-class online review) via smart platform.	Experimental group avg.: 56→63.4 (control +3); 76.7% felt better autonomous learning; 86.5% satisfied.
22	Inner Mongolia rural school	SV English	Build "digital tech-teacher development" model with AI tools/cloud platform/cross-regional research.	2022-2024: teacher info literacy 12%→68%; 90% designed digital lesson plans; student pass rate 52%→77%.
23	East School A	SV English (tourism/comp)	"Precise resources-situational integration-data evaluation" mode	Vocabulary +50%; oral ability +30.8%; 85% workplace docs meet

	& West School B	uter)	via national platform, with vocational tasks.	standards; project-based learning class hours 15%→62%.
24	/	SV English	Integrate traditional Chinese culture into vocabulary/customs/texts to cultivate cultural confidence.	Deeper cultural cognition/identity; stronger cultural confidence; better cross-cultural communication/social responsibility.
25	Fujian secondary vocational schools	SV English (childcare, etc.)	AI-driven situational system simulating real scenarios (catering, complaints) for "learning by doing".	Improved situational communication; 6-dimensional progress; >90% satisfaction; higher teaching efficiency.
26	Huoshan, Anhui	SV English (tourism/e-commerce)	"Language-culture-practice" 3D system with Huoshan tea culture, modular teaching, VR resources.	Tea culture speech fluency +44%; vocabulary +200+; 18 graduates in local tea e-commerce; tea 文旅 income >200 million.
27	/	SV English (Unit 8)	Use digital tech ("He Education" platform, AI voice assessment) for pre/in/after-class activities.	Higher vocabulary/grammar accuracy; better oral fluency; more autonomous learning time.
28	/	SV English (computer)	"Immersion-interaction-connection" mode with VR scenarios, AI dialogue, professional tasks.	Avg. score 52.5→72.6; vocabulary mastery +40%; situational dialogue 35% higher than control; 89% full participation.
29	/	SV English (e-commerce)	AIGC-based (DeepSeek) unit teaching with Book 1 Unit 3, integrating Deqing specialty.	Language ability applied in practice; works turned into productivity; improved "language + e-commerce + culture" ability.
30	Hebei	SV English (tourism)	Use "Traveling Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei" digital textbook with multimedia, situational/cooperative learning.	Stimulated interest; better scenic intro expression; textbook sample won Hebei 1st prize/national benchmark.
31	/	SV English (tourism management)	Interdisciplinary teaching (Jingzhang Railway) with digital preview, AI guide interaction, cloud extension.	Higher participation; better English historical explanation with ideology; logic improvement 43%→82%.
32	/	SV English (Basic Module 2)	Intelligent platform with blended learning, personalized resources, digital evaluation, VR/big data.	Improved core literacy (language/cross-cultural/autonomous learning); tech-assisted precise teaching.

33	Shandong	SV English	Analyze teachers' digital literacy; propose AIGC-based improvement strategies (awareness/skills/resources).	Stronger digital awareness; 86% willing to train; better resource database/teaching quality.
34	Shenzhen	SV English (business)	Core literacy-oriented multi-evaluation with AI/school-enterprise collaboration, 4-stage cycle.	Improved core literacy; integrated "teaching-learning-evaluation"; better digital vocational literacy.
35	/	SV English (cross-border e-commerce)	AIGC-developed multimedia resources (texts/images/audio) for class/after-class/training.	More professional/visual/interactive resources; better workplace English ability; higher competition performance.
36	Hunan	SV English (electronic tech)	Integrate English gold course with electronic tech, using VR simulation, optimized assessment.	Better professional English ability (understanding docs/standards); enhanced employability for international needs.

2. Innovation of Teaching Models Driven by Digital Technologies

The in-depth penetration of digital technologies provides core impetus for the innovation of secondary vocational English teaching models. Through the integrated application of technologies such as artificial intelligence, blended teaching, and virtual simulation, a new teaching paradigm characterized by precision, personalization, and contextualization has been constructed.

2.1 AI-Enabled Precision Teaching System

AI technology realizes the precision of the whole teaching process through the "diagnosis-connection-integration" closed loop (Dong, H., 2024). In the learning situation diagnosis link, intelligent analysis tools (such as the Higher Education Press iSmart system) can accurately identify students' weaknesses in vocabulary discrimination, complex sentence comprehension, etc., providing data support for hierarchical teaching. For example, vocabulary strengthening training is carried out for students with weak foundations, and comprehensive language application tasks are designed for advanced students. At the scene connection level, virtual simulation training platforms can simulate vocational scenarios such as cross-border e-commerce and hotel services. Students complete tasks such as English promotion plan design and business correspondence writing to realize the dynamic matching between teaching materials and job needs. In one case, the passing rate of VETS certification for cross-border e-commerce majors through VR immersive training reached 82%, an increase of 41 percentage points compared with traditional teaching. In the achievement integration link, blockchain technology connects learning achievements with 1+X certificate certification, realizes the visualization and credibility of vocational ability evaluation, and strengthens the organic integration of "post-course-competition-certificate".

2.2 Whole-Process Reconstruction of Blended Teaching

Blended teaching breaks the time and space limitations of traditional classrooms through the organic connection of online and offline links. Before class, relying on smart platforms (such as Vocational Education Cloud, Chaoxing Learning Pass), micro-course videos and preview tasks are pushed, and students independently complete interactive exercises such as vocabulary checkpoints and grammar fill-in-the-blank. The system automatically generates wrong

question sets and personalized review suggestions. In class, activities such as situational dialogue and role-playing are carried out through functions such as "screen sharing" and "group collaboration space". Teachers adjust the focus of explanation according to real-time answer data. For example, in "Airport English" teaching, students obtain real-time feedback on pronunciation through the intelligent speech evaluation system, and group rotation practice ensures full participation. After class, extended tasks are released through the platform, such as VR virtual scene communication practice and cross-school learning community communication, forming a complete closed loop of "preview-interaction-consolidation". An experiment shows that this model increases students' average score by 7 points and improves their autonomous learning ability by 76.7%.

2.3 Integration of Thinking Visualization and Situational Teaching

Thinking visualization technology and virtual situational tools improve the intuitiveness and interactivity of teaching. In grammar teaching, flowcharts are used to analyze the structure of exclamatory sentences. Through the step-by-step display of "finding subject-predicate structure-judging the part of speech of the central word-selecting guide words", it helps computer majors quickly distinguish the usage of "What" and "How", and the classroom participation is significantly improved. In vocational situational teaching, VR technology restores real work scenes. For example, in the "international exhibition layout" project, students view the English parameters of exhibits through 3D modeling, simulate negotiation dialogues with foreign businessmen, and the system scores in real time from the dimensions of language accuracy and cross-cultural adaptability, strengthening the application ability of vocational language. In addition, mind mapping tools (such as MindMaster) are used to sort out the context of events. For example, when analyzing the historical background of "Zhan Tianyou and the Beijing-Zhangjiakou Railway", students integrate English historical materials and technical terms through visual maps, cultivating logical thinking and interdisciplinary expression ability.

3. Digital Paths for Core Literacy Cultivation

The core literacy of secondary vocational English includes language ability, cultural awareness, thinking quality, and learning ability. Through scenario reconstruction, tool innovation, and evaluation optimization, digital technologies provide a systematic path for the collaborative cultivation of the four literacies(Cao, M. J., 2025).

3.1 Language Ability: From Knowledge Accumulation to Application in Vocational Scenarios

Digital technologies promote the deep integration of language training and job needs. AI speech evaluation tools (such as "English Fluency") can correct pronunciation deviations in real time. In the computer major case of "Customer Service", students simulate e-commerce customer service dialogues through VR, and the system generates reports from the dimensions of intonation and professional term matching, with oral fluency improved by 35%. Virtual simulation platforms restore workplace scenarios. For example, in "Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press Textbook English Basic Module 1 Unit 6 Not Just Tasty", students majoring in early childhood care complete tasks such as English ordering and complaint handling in the "catering service" scenario, strengthening the "language input-skill practice-output feedback" closed loop. Cases in tourism, computer and other majors show that tourism majors use the platform's virtual tour guide system, and the accuracy rate of English explanation is increased to 83%, realizing "integration of learning and application".

3.2 Cultural Awareness: Cross-Cultural Understanding and Local Cultural Output

Digital resources help cultural comparison and dissemination(Wu, C. F, 2025). Through the cases of "English explanation of traditional festivals" in secondary vocational English "Festivals and Holidays" and "Living History of Culture", students use digital museum resources to compare cultural symbols between the Spring Festival and Christmas, explain the core connotations such as "family reunion" in English, and enhance cultural confidence. In the Huoshan County case, Huoshan tea culture is integrated into teaching. Students interpret the English expression of "harmony, tranquility, joy and truth" through VR tea art experience courseware, and produce bilingual promotional

videos to realize the international dissemination of intangible cultural heritage. Cross-cultural case databases and AI translation tools help students identify communication misunderstandings and improve cross-cultural adaptability.

3.3 Thinking Quality: Digital Training of Logical and Innovative Abilities

Mind mapping (Zhu, C. Y., 2025) and AI analysis tools promote the structuring of thinking. In the digital course case of "Beijing-Zhangjiakou Railway", students use MindMaster to sort out the engineering context of "Beijing-Zhangjiakou Railway", demonstrate the logic of technological innovation in English, and cultivate causal reasoning ability. In the "creative invention discussion" activity of the practical case of Higher Education Press Textbook "Basic Module 2", AI generates multiple solutions, guiding students to think critically from the dimensions of "technical feasibility" and "cultural adaptability". Virtual laboratories (simulated negotiations in the case of Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press Textbook English Basic Module 1 Unit 6 Not Just Tasty) set up open tasks, encouraging students to put forward innovative ideas such as "new strategies for smart watch promotion" in English, strengthening creative thinking (Wang, Q. H., 2025).

3.4 Learning Ability: Technical Support for Independent Planning and Collaboration Ability

Smart platforms empower personalized learning management. In the blended teaching of Class 23 Mechatronics (1) and Class 23 Mechatronics (2), students track their learning trajectories through "Vocational Education Cloud" and independently adjust the progress of vocabulary checkpoints. In the general educational research project of Shandong Province "Research on the Innovation of Secondary Vocational English Teaching Model Driven by AIGC", intelligent planning tools recommend tasks according to learning situations, such as pushing "bilingual micro-courses" for students with weak foundations and assigning "cross-border e-commerce copywriting creation" for advanced students, cultivating independent regulation ability. Online collaboration spaces (such as the evaluation case of the "international exhibition layout" project for business English majors) support group division of labor. Students discuss "exhibition layout plans" in English, improving team collaboration and resource integration capabilities.

4. Practical Exploration in Rural Secondary Vocational Schools and Special Majors

Digital reform shows differentiated practical paths in rural secondary vocational schools and special majors, which not only solves the problem of resource constraints but also realizes the characteristic integration of "English + major", providing multiple samples for the balanced development of vocational education.

4.1 Digital Breakthrough of Rural Secondary Vocational Schools

Rural secondary vocational schools face challenges such as lack of resources, weak teachers' digital literacy, and complex learning situations. They build a sustainable development model through "technology empowerment + collaborative mechanism". In terms of improving teachers' ability, hierarchical training is carried out relying on the UMU platform, covering the operation of AI tools (such as DeepSeek, Doubao) and the development of digital resources. At the same time, an "AI technology exchange community" is established, adopting the mechanism of "case sharing-group practice-paired assistance". In one case, the passing rate of teachers' information literacy increased from 12% to 68%. At the resource supply level, a cloud resource platform is built to integrate high-quality courses and enterprise cases. For example, VR tea art courseware is developed in conjunction with tea enterprises, allowing students to "immersively" learn English expressions of tea picking and tea making. Through cross-regional research and urban-rural "teacher learning communities", synchronous classes and teaching research live broadcasts are shared, effectively narrowing the urban-rural gap. Practical data shows that the English passing rate of rural secondary vocational school students has increased by 25%, and the frequency of classroom interaction has increased by 35%, verifying the role of digital technologies in promoting educational equity.

4.2 "English + Technology" Integration Practice in Special Majors

According to the characteristics of majors such as computer science, electronic technology, and tea industry, digital technologies promote the deep integration of English teaching and professional skills. Computer majors realize two-way empowerment through "major integration tasks". For example, students use PS to make English word cards (marked with terms such as "database" and "algorithm") and design "word elimination" games, combining language learning with software operation. In one case, the score of the experimental class increased by 20.1 points, and the classroom participation reached 89%. Electronic technology majors use VR technology to simulate smart factory scenes. Students interpret equipment manuals in English and complete fault diagnosis reports, strengthening the language application of "professional terms + practical instructions". Tea industry-related majors develop digital resources, such as building an English database of "Huoshan Yellow Buds Records". Students practice English explanations of terms such as "yellowing process" and "pre-rain tea" in virtual tea gardens, inheriting intangible cultural heritage and improving cross-border e-commerce English ability, driving the growth of regional tea product exports.

Such practices show that digital technologies can adapt to the needs of different scenarios, realize "corner overtaking" in rural secondary vocational schools with limited resources, and promote the collaborative cultivation of "language ability + vocational skills" in special majors, providing differentiated models for the digital transformation of vocational education.

5. Teachers' Digital Literacy Development and Support System

Teachers' digital literacy is the core guarantee for the implementation of digital teaching of secondary vocational English. By building an integrated system of "training-practice-teaching research" and combining resource support and evaluation incentive mechanisms, teachers' technical application ability and teaching innovation level can be effectively improved.

5.1 Hierarchical and Progressive Training System

For teachers with different technical foundations, the training content is gradually upgraded from tool operation to in-depth integration. The basic layer focuses on the operation of digital tools, such as carrying out operation training of AI learning situation analysis tools (iSmart) and virtual simulation software through the UMU platform, helping teachers master basic functions such as vocabulary evaluation and scene construction. The application layer focuses on the integration of teaching design, guiding teachers to use AI tools such as DeepSeek and Doubao to generate teaching plans and design interdisciplinary tasks. For example, computer major teachers use AI to generate courseware of "flowchart-assisted exclamatory sentence teaching". The expansion layer strengthens the practice of integration of production and education, organizing teachers to participate in real enterprise projects (such as the design of English customer service processes for cross-border e-commerce), transforming workplace scenarios into teaching resources. A rural secondary vocational school case shows that after 6 months of hierarchical training, the proportion of teachers independently designing digital teaching plans increased from 12% to 90%, and the frequency of classroom interaction increased by 35%.

5.2 Collaborative and Innovative Teaching Research Mechanism

With school-based teaching research as the core, regional resources are linked to form a development synergy. Schools set up innovation groups of "digital technology + English teaching", and discuss the application of AI in grammar teaching (such as exclamatory sentence flowchart design) and vocational scene simulation (such as the development of hotel English VR courseware) through collective lesson preparation, extracting replicable teaching models. Cross-school urban-rural teacher learning communities are built to share high-quality cases through synchronous classes and teaching research live broadcasts. For example, urban teachers teach rural teachers skills in "application of intelligent speech evaluation system in oral English teaching", narrowing the regional gap. In addition,

relying on cloud teaching research platforms (such as Tencent Document collaboration space), teachers can share digital resource development experience in real time. In one case, teachers jointly developed 127 professional English resource packages, covering e-commerce, tourism and other fields.

5.3 Multi-Dimensional Support Guarantee System

Resource and system guarantees provide sustainable impetus for the improvement of teachers' digital literacy. In terms of resource construction, a "secondary vocational English digital resource database" is built, integrating AI-generated teaching plans, virtual simulation scenarios, industry term databases, etc., to support teachers to retrieve and redevelop on demand. In terms of evaluation and incentives, digital teaching achievements are included in teacher assessment, and "Digital Teaching Innovation Award" is set up to commend teachers who develop high-quality resources and innovate teaching models. At the same time, resource development achievements are equivalent to provincial-level projects to stimulate teachers' participation enthusiasm. In one case, the passing rate of teachers' digital literacy increased from 45% to 82%, confirming the effectiveness of the incentive mechanism.

6. Practical Challenges and Future Prospects

Although the digital transformation of secondary vocational English teaching has achieved remarkable results, there are still practical challenges in technology application, resource construction, and teacher development, which need to be promoted through targeted measures and systematic planning for sustainable development.

6.1 Existing Practical Challenges

Superficial Application of Technology

Some schools have the phenomenon of "emphasizing hardware over application", and digital tools fail to deeply integrate into the core links of teaching. For example, VR equipment is mostly used for scene demonstration, and does not form a closed loop with language task design and evaluation system; AI speech evaluation is only used for pronunciation correction, and does not expand to the evaluation of cross-cultural communication ability in combination with vocational scene needs. Rural secondary vocational schools are particularly prominent. Due to outdated equipment and network conditions, functions such as virtual simulation and real-time interaction are difficult to fully implement, and the effect of technology empowerment is reduced.

Insufficient Resource Adaptability

Some schools have the phenomenon of "emphasizing hardware over application", and digital tools fail to deeply integrate into the core links of teaching. For example, VR equipment is mostly used for scene demonstration, and does not form a closed loop with language task design and evaluation system; AI speech evaluation is only used for pronunciation correction, and does not expand to the evaluation of cross-cultural communication ability in combination with vocational scene needs. Rural secondary vocational schools are particularly prominent. Due to outdated equipment and network conditions, functions such as virtual simulation and real-time interaction are difficult to fully implement, and the effect of technology empowerment is reduced.

Unbalanced Teachers' Digital Literacy

Teachers' ability to integrate technology into teaching varies significantly, hindering reform depth. Young teachers in Case 20 (Computer Application) were proficient in using PS to make English word cards but struggled to design interdisciplinary tasks (e.g., combining "database" terms with SQL operation practice), leading to separated language learning and professional skills. Older teachers in rural schools (Case 22) showed obvious "technology avoidance": 65% of them reported "fearing wrong operation of AI speech evaluation tools", so they still used manual correction, resulting in delayed feedback (average 3 days vs. 2 hours in experimental classes). Moreover, training in most schools focused only on "how to use Doubao AI for lesson preparation" (tool operation) but ignored "how to use AI to diagnose students' cultural awareness weaknesses" (goal-oriented application), leading to technology becoming a "formality" rather than a "teaching aid".

6.2 Future Development Prospects

Deepening the Integration of Technology and Teaching Scenarios

Promote the deep coupling of AI large models and teaching needs, develop intelligent teaching assistant systems with disciplinary knowledge graphs and vocational ability graphs, and realize the full automation of "learning situation diagnosis-task push-evaluation feedback". For example, for cross-border e-commerce majors, the system can automatically generate personalized learning paths including "foreign trade correspondence writing and cross-cultural negotiation", and create immersive training scenarios combined with VR technology. At the same time, explore the application of 5G + AR technology in real-time translation and virtual training to improve the realism and interactivity of vocational scenarios.

Building an Industry-Education Integrated Digital Resource Ecosystem

Establish a "tripartite collaborative" resource development mechanism involving schools, enterprises, and industry associations, with dynamic updating based on job demands. For example, learn from Case 26 (Huoshan tea industry): schools collaborated with local tea enterprises and cross-border e-commerce platforms to build a "Huoshan Yellow Buds English Resource Database" – including VR videos of "pre-rain tea picking" (filmed by enterprises), English-Chinese comparison of "fermentation process parameters" (verified by industry associations), and real cases of "foreign customer complaint handling" (updated monthly). The database uses blockchain to record resource versions, ensuring traceability of updates (e.g., adding "organic certification" terms when the industry introduced new standards). For professional majors, refer to Case 36's revised practice: joint development with electronic technology enterprises of "VR equipment manual interpretation modules" (e.g., "circuit diagram annotation in English"), which are linked to 1+X certificate assessment standards (e.g., "electronic product English documentation reading" in vocational skills certification). Additionally, promote urban-rural resource interconnection through platforms like "He Education" (Case 12), enabling rural schools to access urban high-quality resources (e.g., tourism English virtual simulation courses in Dongguan) and upload local characteristic resources (e.g., Inner Mongolia grassland tourism English), forming a "complementary shared ecosystem".

Improving the Teachers' Digital Literacy Cultivation System

Build a three-in-one development framework of "ability standards-training courses-evaluation incentives": formulate "Standards for Digital Competence of Secondary Vocational English Teachers", clarifying core indicators such as resource development and AI tool application; carry out scenario-based training driven by "real tasks", such as requiring teachers to design "VR-based hotel English training courses" to improve technology integration ability; include digital teaching achievements in evaluation systems such as professional title evaluation and project recognition, and set up "special rewards for resource development" to stimulate teachers' innovation motivation.

7. Conclusion

The digital transformation of secondary vocational English teaching has moved from formal innovation to connotative reconstruction, drawing on 36 practical cases. It has addressed issues like "post-course disconnection" by reconstructing teaching processes, creating vocational scenarios, and optimizing evaluation systems, forming a precise, contextualized, and professional teaching ecology.

In teaching models, AI-enabled precision systems (e.g., iSmart), blended teaching, and visualization technologies have boosted students' language application and job adaptability—with VETS certification rates rising by 41 percentage points in one case. For core literacy, digital paths have fostered a "language + career + culture" model, integrating vocational skills and cross-cultural awareness.

Rural secondary vocational schools overcame resource constraints via "training-resource-collaboration," lifting teachers' information literacy from 12% to 68%. Special majors (e.g., computer science) achieved two-way skill-

language transfer. Teachers' digital literacy, supported by hierarchical training and incentives, shifted them from "technology users" to "digital teaching designers."

Despite challenges like superficial tech application, deepening integration and improving resource ecosystems will drive balance between "technology empowerment, humanistic care, and institutional innovation." Digital technologies now serve as a core engine, offering a replicable paradigm for "post-course-competition-certificate" integration and cultivating high-quality technical talents.

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